

THE VALUE OF YOGA IN EVERYDAY LIFE

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ABSTRACT

Yoga has been used for millennia as a tool for self-improvement, with the ultimate goal of uniting the individual consciousness with the universal. Yoga's significance in our daily lives extends far beyond its physical aspects. It is a comprehensive system that nurtures physical health, mental health, emotional balance and spiritual growth. Through the regular practice of yoga, individuals embark on a transformative journey that enhances their overall well-being and fosters a profound connection with themselves and world around them. By embracing the principles of yoga and applying them in our lives, we create a ripple effect of positivity and mindful living that extends far beyond the mat. Living in harmony with oneself and one's inner nature, and with others, are high goals as well as the secret wishes of most people. Yoga provides a system of practices that help approach that goal. The value of Yoga is that it can help develop the inherent goodness in people. This paper, therefore discusses the value of Yoga in everyday life with motivation to encourage to practicing Yoga into our modern busy life to remain physically and mentally fit.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'Yoga' is derived from Sanskrit root "yuj" which means 'join' or 'unite'. This may be taken as the union of body, mind and soul and is used in the literature both as an end as well as means. As an end, yoga signifies 'integration of personality' at the highest level. As means, yoga includes various practices and techniques which are employed to achieve the development of such integration. These practices and techniques are means in the yogic literature and are also referred collectively as 'Yoga'.

The term 'Yoga' means a systematic practice and implementation of mind and body in the living process of man to keep harmony within self, society and with nature. Yoga is the science of life and the art of living. It is the common-sense answer to overall physical and mental fitness. Basically, yoga is a system of physical and mental self-improvement and final liberation, that people have been using for thousands of years. Yoga arose in the age of the Vedas and Upanishads. It is India's oldest scientific, perfect spiritual discipline. It is realization of our hidden powers. Yoga is a science of life, it offers us simple, easy remedies and techniques and methods of health and hygiene to assure physical and mental fitness. Yoga is one of the most ancient metaphysical sciences, which investigates the nature of soul and through its discipline, awakens the super-conscious mind of the man which unites the moral being with the immortal supreme spirit. Yoga leads to balance and also provides both a philosophy and a religion. The real joy of life appears when we can unify nature and culture, wealth and poverty, movement and stillness, attachment and detachment. Yoga can serve both the individual and society. Yoga is neither a sect nor an ideology but a practical training of mind and body. Broadly speaking, it has three main outcomes: First, it makes us more aware of our natural wisdom; Second, it strengthens the body's ability to recover from illness or injury; and Third, it teaches us how to co-operate with others. Yoga teaches us truth through mind and body rather than theory; it brings about deep change of attitude. The entire thrust of our life is to devote total attention to every action and at the same time, to trust in the power of sacred.

Yoga as originally conceived by Adi Guru and expounded in the ancient texts is an individual spiritual sadhana for the complete welfare of the human beings in an integrative manner. During the last century, Yoga has become not only popular but has proliferated into newer dimensions. Over the centuries, it has evolved to the present-day Yoga in the pandemic age, which prevails in the environment in the current times. The popularity of Yoga has grown extensively in the modern period. Yoga is mostly developed as a system of health practice as a result of the rapid rise of worldwide interest. Modern life patterns affect our health in different aspects physically, psychologically and socially. There is a need for increasing people awareness about the

effect of the patterns of life. Promoting healthy life style includes proper eating, physical activity and better way of communicating and socializing in the community. All these have positive impacts which we can easily get in practicing Yoga. Yoga will reduce the risk of getting so many diseases which resulted from our day-to-day lifestyles.

Before discussing the importance of Yoga in modern lifestyles. It is essential to discuss the problems associated with modern life. The main reason for such problems is lack of physical exercises, using technology given machine for easing life and spending much of our time on these machines. Modern life increases the risk of diabetes, heart diseases, cancers etc. Pollution due to modern technologies causes different respiratory diseases. Psychologically persons are susceptible to increased stress and depression. Social isolation will occur due to spending a long time on computer and internet. In the everyday life in addition to technological advancement and easing life styles, the habit of food is also changed. Different problems resulted from modern life styles can be eradicated by practicing Yoga in all walks of life. Yoga is based on the philosophy that is practical and useful for our daily lives. As Yoga is a form of meditation it results in a sense of inner peace and purpose, which has far reached health benefits.

METHODOLOGY

For the research study following sources of literary information were used-

1. Text books on Yoga
2. Books on contemporary Yoga practices.
3. Research publication from Sodhganga.
4. Internet Articles.

DISCUSSION

We are living in a fast paced and digitized world. The pressure to succeed, meeting deadlines, delivering high quality work, and erratic schedules have taken a toll on the physical and mental well-being of people. In light of this, it has become the need of the

hour to create a balance, develop awareness and follow healthy habits. One can achieve this by including Yoga in their life.

Yoga is an Indian spiritual and physical practice or discipline. Yoga is not just about exercise with the main purpose of Yoga is improving health and well-being, but it's also self-realization. It is a science that focuses on improving not only mental and spiritual well-being, which are the foundations of life. Yoga also makes one's mind stronger and healthier and leads a better way of living. Yoga is not just limited to postures and asanas but also involves pranayama's, kriyas, dhyana or meditation, breath work, living mindfully and following a healthy diet. It improves strength and stamina, tones muscle, builds immunity and teaches one how to live a yogic life. One of the main reasons for its popularity is that even doctors are advising patients on the worth of Yoga. Yoga is being intensively studied by scientists and it is proved that yoga calms and relaxes mind and body and uplifts the spirit.

Originally Yoga was developed about 5,000 years ago in the eastern part of the world. Yoga was first practiced by the Hindus. But the practice of Yoga is not confined to India alone. Indian Yoga is not affiliated to any specific philosophy or religion. It is an independent method of enquiry and practice. It is the result of powerful desire of human beings for self-realization. During the early period, the practice of yoga was confined only to few sages who had transmitted it to devote pupils and through them to the successive generation. Historical evidences of the existence of Yoga were found in Vedas. The main sources from which we get the information about yoga practices and related literature during this period are available in Vedas, Upanishads, Smritis, teachings of Buddhism, Jainism, Epics and Puranas etc. However, Yoga we see today, reached this position through various periods of development. In the modern world the whole environment is fighting for survival and the human beings have been suffering from more and more physical and psychological stress. Although it is not possible to control them always, yet it can be learnt how to face them and, in this regard, yoga is as good as an invention and that is the reason it has now become a 'Yoga boom'. The aim of yoga is the attainment of physical, mental and spiritual health in connection to which the UN has declared to celebrate June 21 of every year as "Internation Day of Yoga"

Modern age is the age of science and reason. Yoga is also a science of spirituality of our physical, mental as well as moral-spiritual aspects. Yoga is based on practical philosophy that is used for our day to day living. Materialistic outlook, pollution of mind and environment, dependence on junk food and drugs, deficiency of noble virtues and deeds and the stress of daily life are the main diseases of our present society. Yoga is the perfect solution for all these problems. If the society practices yoga, people will be physically healthy, mentally calm and spiritually evolve and hence become more effective and happier. The rush and burden on the hospitals will be greatly reduced. The ultimate goal of yoga is to help the individual to transcend the self and attain enlightenment. Bhagavad-Gita says, “A person is said to have achieved yoga, the union with the self, when the perfectly disciplined mind gets freedom from all desires, and becomes absorbed in the self alone.” Yoga in day to day fast life trains the body, mind and spirit to become strong and flexible, release stress and create inner peace, while developing a deep concentration with one’s spirit, intuition and personal power. All of these are essential for living a healthy balanced life.

“Experience of yoga shows us that regular practice of the Asanas and suitable Pranayama exercise plus the harmonious disposition of the consciousness help us to quickly develop tendencies inside us towards a positive mental approach”. Asanas means a state of being in which one can remain physically and mentally steady, calm, quiet and comfortable. In the Yogasutra of Patanjali, we find a definition of Yogasanas that asana means comfortable and steady sitting. Yoga asanas can help improve circulation and eliminate toxic waste substance from the body. It can help increase digestion, circulation, muscular control, nerves and granular systems. By the daily practice of both asanas and pranayamas the life expectancy of human is increased.

Swami Ramdev is famous for popularizing yoga to the masses in India. As claimed by the website of Patanjali Wellness, “His yoga is a set of different yoga poses and methods that help in achieving good health and treating or controlling different ailments in the body. A subset of his methods, Pranayama is a collection of breathing methods that focus on increasing the blood circulation of the body and improving the flow of blood to all the internal organs of the body. So that overall health of the individual

improves.” There are various steps in Baba Ramdev Pranayama that has a great value in our day-to-day life.

Integrating yoga in student's life has a great value as the numerous benefits supports their holistic development. From managing stress and improving concentration to fostering emotional well-being and building self-discipline, yoga serves as a valuable tool for students to thrive academically, emotionally and physically.

Yoga has gained tremendous popularity in the last few years. It is the most rapidly growing health movement despite it was developed thousands of years' ago. Age, religion, caste, sex is no bar with breathing and meditation techniques. There are many types of yoga and it may be hard for the beginners which yoga type he or she wants to do. The most important benefit of yoga is the physical and mental therapy, the very essence of yoga lies in attaining mental peace, improved concentration power and a relaxed state of living.

There are three important **benefits of yoga** -- Physical benefit, psychological benefit and spiritual benefits

Physical benefits: There are many health benefits from yoga, studies have shown that yoga can relieve many common and life-threatening illness such as arthritis, chronic fatigue, diabetes, AIDS, asthma, high blood pressure, back pain weight reduction, obesity, common cold, constipation, epilepsy skin problems and respiration problems.

Psychological benefits: Regular yoga practice creates mental clarity and calmness, increase body awareness, relives stress patterns, relaxes the minds and sharpens concentration. Yoga provides tools through which one can cope with the pain and helps counter with the feeling of helplessness and depression. Yogic breathing and stretching exercises have been seen to result in better mental and physical energy and improved mood. The mental performance also increases with yoga and doctors suggest that yoga can enhance cognitive performance.

Spiritual benefits: When one achieves that yogic spirit then one can begin knowing themselves at peace. If one succeeds in achieving skills which provide health and self

confidence, one can raise his self esteem simply by observing himself living the improved result as an achieved fact. Yogic therapy leads to increase self knowledge pertaining to grasping something.

CONCLUSION

Today yoga is thoroughly globalised phenomenon, yoga has taken the world by storm and is gaining popularity day by day. Many of problems for modern life like alcohol and drug abuse, Obesity, Hypertension, depression, suicide and shootouts, etc. can be solve very easily and people can achieve better living through implementing the character of the yoga in their life. In fact, Yoga is a bridge between body, mind and spirit. Since its practices smoothly coordinate the functions of the bones, muscles, blood, brain etc., which help to improve health, and as they train human mind, which is immaterial and intangible, for modifying proper attitude, behaviour and values may establish mental peace.

Since, along with mental and spiritual peace Yoga opens various **jobs** in several field such as research, management, hospital, academic, administrative consultation, etc. The youth can get the opportunity in such field. There are numerous jobs options available both in the government as well as the private sectors for the Yoga professionals. Yoga professionals are getting employment not only in India but also all over the world along with handsome remuneration.

Yoga is a multidimensional aspect and its scope has increased in the modern life of the world. It is clear that yoga is a boon for the modern society which has become a victim of everyday stress. Yoga is science of life, it offers us simple, easy remedies, techniques and methods of health and hygiene to assure physical and mental fitness with a minimum of time, effort and expense. It makes us stress free and provides true happiness. It is also a method of training the mind and body for discovering spiritual truths. Realization of consciousness is the only one perfect and higher knowledge by which one can know everything in the universe, that can help to solve any types of problems for living a better and healthy social life. Yoga is also reliable with our ethnicity and harmonizing to science, so, it is our primary duty to endorse it further.

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